

Synthetic 3D Breast MRI Generation using Diffusion Models

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Abstract

Breast cancer is, as of today, the cancer with the biggest incidence worldwide, as well as one of the leading cause for cancer-related deaths. Traditional tumour characterisation and localisation procedures are usually invasive, imprecise and non-reproducible, so imaging techniques such as MRIs are considered invaluable and are often used for oncological diagnosis and surgery planning. However, MRI screening procedures generate a fundamental problem, for which there is still no solution: how is it possible to quantify how the breast (a highly deformable organ) changes shape according to patient's position. For example, even though MRIs are done in the prone position, surgery is mostly done in supine, thus it is hard for surgeons to correctly assess the position and shape of the tumour having only seen prone MRIs. The answer comes in the form of hybrid physics-inspired biomechanical models that can process, comprehend and apply this prone to supine transformation of the 3D medical scans, with the intent of predicting the tumours' location, shape and overall characteristics. For such a model to be constructed, however, a great amount of realistic data is required, this being a hard and time-consuming process.

This work describes the first steps towards this issue: the introduction of generative deep learning models to increase the existing amount of realistic and usable 3D breast MRI scans. These aim to understand and mimic the intricacies of breast MRI anatomy, thus creating realistic and non patient-specific 3D scans that can then contribute to the required data augmentation. The results obtained can be recognised as a valuable contribution in the field of medical image generation, especially taking into consideration that literature in this field is, in its great majority, a novelty. The methodology used proves also to be a valid pipeline for the generation of such images by introducing post-processing methods and also super-resolution techniques.

Keywords: Diffusion Models; Artificial Intelligence; Non-Conditional Image Generation; MRI Acquisition

1 Introduction

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is an imaging technique used throughout the globe with the intent of extracting reproducible measures in regards to all sorts of anatomical tissue and structures. Unlike other techniques though, it utilises strong magnetic fields rather than ionising radiation in order to produce high-quality scans. This is done by capitalising on the properties of the body's water molecules, more specifically the hydrogen atoms' proton and how these emit energy when under controlled radiofrequency pulses.

MRIs are particularly useful as an imaging technique for the characterisation of breast tumours and other abnormalities seeing as it offers a relatively high sensitivity and specificity, when compared to more conventional methods such as mammography or ultrasound. This is especially true for clinical cases in which the tumour is either small or in an early stage, due to MRIs being able to discern the lesion from sometimes very dense breast tissue. If used in conjunction with other contrast enhancement techniques, some information on the tumour's malignancy and size can also be acquired, helping physicians to continually monitor and adjust treatment based on the ailment's progression.

Diffusion models, on the other hand, have recently emerged as one of the most powerful classes of generative models when it comes to the creation of high-quality synthetic data, including images, audio and even video. Also, as of the present, they are considered to be the state-of-the-art for media generation, when compared to all other techniques such as Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), as proved by Dhariwal and Nichol [1]. This is done by learning the underlying data distribution for the training dataset and gradually transforming gaussian noise into coherent and detailed output, thus attempting to mimic the phenomenon physical diffusion.

Even though they have been applied to a number of tasks such as denoising or inpainting, diffusion models excel, at least when applied to this problem, in creating synthetic MRI scans which are indistinguishable from real ones. Therefore, by relying on carefully curated training data and robust architectures, these provide a way to expand existing datasets and significantly reduce the need for additional data acquisition.

2 Methodology

In order to generate a good amount of artificial samples for 3D MRI scans various different architectures were implemented and experimented with. Due to computational constraints, however, and because of the complexity of the standard breast MRI scan, only low resolution samples were created, these being of size 64×64 and 128×128 . The idea behind this aims to lessen the burden on the generative model and perfect the existing spatial coherence between samples, as well as the connectivity between the different tissues depicted in the samples. Resolution enhancement is done afterwards using different GAN-based architectures, in a process we call **Super-Resolution**, so as to ensure that generated samples are up to the quality in which clinicians are used to seeing them in.

Moreover, while various experiments were performed in order to fine-tune the best training parameters, the training data has been kept mostly the same, albeit for different dataset splits. This consists of a combination of two datasets: a public one comprised of all the samples in the **Duke Breast Cancer MRI Dataset**; and a private limited amount of samples provided by the **Fundação Champalimaud**. Despite some differences between the acquisition procedures for both datasets, this has been done so intentionally, with the intent of creating a model that would adapt to the project's needs and also to different data sources.

2.1 Video Diffusion

The first utilised architecture utilised in this project was initially presented by Ho *et al.* [2], and represented a key advancement in video generation by being one of the first papers to present a 3D diffusion model. The transition between 2D and 3D created many challenges, namely the preservation of both spatial and temporal coherence between the different structures as well as the different frames / MRI slices. This was achieved mainly by using a factorised space-time U-Net architecture, rather than the traditional one and also by conditioning the gradient values so as to increase the quality of its non-conditional generative process.

Lastly, it would be relevant to mention that this model has been used as the baseline for this task, since its architecture (in figure 1) is comparably quite simple and also because it has shown incredible results with

the natural looking data it was originally trained on.

Figure 1: Video Diffusion Model's Architecture consisting of the traditional diffusion model U-Net but adapted to 3D generation

2.2 Masked Conditional Video Diffusion

The second model chosen for the task at hand was the MCVD by Voleti *et al.* [4], which could handle multiple tasks such as video generation, video prediction and frame interpolation, of which we would only use the non-conditional video generation aspect. The architecture chosen for this model was, contrastingly, that of a 2D U-Net for reasons of computational efficiency, though this can more easily lead to spatial incoherence between the different MRI volume slices, seeing as different frames are not generated as a whole and have less connectivity between each other.

2.3 Medical Diffusion

Lastly, the final methodology employed was introduced by Khader *et al.* [3] specifically for the generation of 3D medical imaging data. Despite using the same Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model (DDPM) architecture as the last two, it can be considered more suitable to this task due to the efficient patch-based training approach it employs, which aims to split the 3D volume into patches for a reduction of both the necessary memory as well as the amount of training time when using larger datasets. Moreover, since it was trained for this specific task on various medical imaging datasets, including the Duke Breast Cancer MRI dataset, this model is clearly a perfect fit for the task presented.

2.4 Post-Processing & Evaluation

Upon implementation of the aforementioned architectures, computational hurdles quickly became apparent, namely how artificial samples would need to be generated in a lower resolution, so as to fit a reasonable training time frame. This was circumvented by using a GAN-based super-resolution, which would turn the models' output into higher quality 3D volumes, preparing them for evaluation from radiologists, who typically are used to seeing MRI scans in very high image sizes. The model used for this was the **Real Enhanced Super Resolution Generative Adversarial Network (Real-ESRGAN)** presented by Wang *et al.* [5].

It would also be of substance to mention that in order to evaluate the results in a more quantitative way, various standard generative-related metrics were used, including but not limited to Multi-Scale Structural Similarity Index (*MS-SSIM*) and Fréchet Inception Distance (*FID*).

3 Results

Preliminary results with the Video Diffusion model for the lower resolution (64×64) samples in figure 2 have proved to be of good quality. However, and perhaps due to the discrepancies between the two datasets that it was trained on, results are quite grainy and require a great deal of post-processing and smoothing before even being fed to the super-resolution model mentioned, which is not ideal.

On the other hand, experiments with the Medical Diffusion models for a higher frame size of 128×128 have been a lot more successful in emulating the properties of real-life breast MRI volumes and have only displayed a slight amount of noise, as seen in figure 3, which are easily removable. These favourable results have also been verified by the chosen evaluation metrics. Both were followed by the use of super-resolution.

Figure 2: Two examples of non-enhanced 64×64 3D samples created using the Video Diffusion model in .gif format

Figure 3: Two examples of non-enhanced 128×128 3D samples created using the Medical Diffusion model in .gif format

4 Conclusions

Using these methodologies, we prove that a high-resolution 3D breast MRI generator pipeline is, if using the right models, a valid solution for the lack of data currently plaguing the medical machine learning community. This is also a valuable stepping stone for the inclusion of anatomical conditional variables in the generation of patient-specific volumes which may be under-represented in modern datasets.

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